

Inverse Coefficient Analysis in Semi-Linear Parabolic Heat Conduction Models

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Abstract

In this study, we examine a coefficient problem for the inverse problem of a quasilinear pseudo-parabolic equation with periodic boundary conditions. By employing an iterative method, we establish the existence and uniqueness of the solution.

1. Introduction

Inverse problems are the problems that consist of finding an unknown property of an object, or a medium, from the observation of a response of this object, or medium, to a probing signal. Thus, the theory of inverse problems yields a theoretical basis for remote sensing and non-destructive evaluation. For example, if an acoustic plane wave is scattered by an obstacle, and one observes the scattered field far from the obstacle, or in some exterior region, then the inverse problem is to find the shape and material properties of the obstacle. Such problems are important in identification of flying objects (airplanes missiles, etc.), objects immersed in water (submarines, paces of fish, etc.) and in many other situations. In geophysics one sends an acoustic wave from the surface of the earth and collects the scattered field on the surface for various positions of the source of the field for a fixed frequency, or for several frequencies. The inverse problem is to find the subsurface in homogeneities. In technology one measures the eigen frequencies of a piece of a material, and the inverse problem is to find a defect in this material, for example, a hole in a metal. In geophysics the inhomogeneity can be an oil deposit, a cave, a mine. In medicine it may be a tumor or some abnormality in a human body. If one is able to find in homogeneities in a medium by processing the scattered field on the surface, then one does not have to drill a hole in a medium. This, in turn, avoids expensive and destructive evaluation. The practical advantages of remote sensing are what make the inverse problems important. Over the last couple of years,

considerable efforts have been put in to develop either approximate analytical solution or purely numerical solution to nonlocal boundary value problems implemented finite difference scheme to obtain numerical solution of value problem the one-dimensional nonlocal boundary value problem (see, e.g., [1-6]). The periodic boundary conditions arise from many important applications in heat transfer, life sciences. In [7, 8], Bağlan and Kanca are worked to these conditions.

Let $T > 0$ be fixed number and denote by $D := \{0 < x < \pi, 0 < t < T\}$.

Consider the problem of finding a pair of functions $\{j(t), u(x,t)\}$ satisfying the following equations:

$$\partial u / \partial t - \partial^2 u / \partial x^2 - \alpha \partial^3 u / \partial x^2 t - j(t)u = f(x,t,u), \quad (1)$$

$$u(0,t) = u(\pi,t), \quad t \in [0,T], \quad (2)$$

$$u_x(0,t) = u_x(\pi,t), \quad t \in [0,T], \quad (3)$$

$$u(x,0) = \varphi(x), \quad x \in [0,\pi], \quad (4)$$

$$s(t) = \int_0^\pi x u(x,t) dx, \quad t \in [0,T] \quad (4)$$

for a quasilinear parabolic equation with the nonlinear source term $f(x,t,u)$. The function $\varphi(x)$ and $f(x,t,u)$ are given functions on $[0,\pi]$ and D respectively. Denote the solution of problem (1)-(3) by $u(x,t)$

Definition 1. The pair $\{j(t), u(x,t)\}$ of (1)-(4) are satisfied is called the classical solution of the inverse problem (1)-(4).

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2. Existence and Uniqueness of the Solution of Inverse Problem

We denote the solution of system (1) by

$$\begin{aligned}
 u(x,t) = & \frac{1}{2} \left(\varphi_0 e^{\int_0^t j(\tau) d\tau} + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi f(x,t,u) dx dt \right) \\
 & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \varphi_{ck} e^{\frac{-(2k)^2 t}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} - \int_0^t j(\tau) d\tau} \cos 2kx \\
 & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{\pi(1+\varepsilon(2k)^2)} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi e^{\frac{-(2k)^2(t-\tau)}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} - \int_0^\tau j(\tau) d\tau} \cos 2kx f(x,t,u) dx dt \right) \cos 2kx \\
 & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \varphi_{sk} e^{\frac{-(2k)^2 t}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} - \int_0^t j(\tau) d\tau} \sin 2kx \\
 & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{\pi(1+\varepsilon(2k)^2)} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi e^{\frac{-(2k)^2(t-\tau)}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} - \int_0^\tau j(\tau) d\tau} \sin 2kx f(x,t,u) dx dt \right) \sin 2kx
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varphi_0 &= \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) dx, \\
 \varphi_{ck} &= \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \cos 2kx dx, \\
 \varphi_{sk} &= \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \sin 2kx dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 1. Suppose that the following conditions hold:

- (A1) $s(t) \in C^1[0, T]$.
- (A2) $\varphi(x) \in C^{[3,3]}[0, \pi]$.
- (A3) $f(x, t, u)$ is provided following conditions:
 - 1) $f(x, t, u) \in C^{(2,2,0)}(D)$,
 - 2) $\left| \frac{\partial f(x, t, u)}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial f(x, t, \bar{u})}{\partial x} \right| \leq b(x, t) |u - \bar{u}|$,

where $b(x, t) \in L_2(D)$ is Lipschitz coefficients.

Condition (4) can be differentiated under the assumptions (A1)-(A3),

$$s'(t) = \int_0^\pi x u_t dx, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T$$

then the unknown coefficient is obtained in this form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 j(t) = & \frac{1}{s(t)} \left[-s'(t) + \frac{\pi^2}{2} f_0 \right] \\
 & + \frac{\pi}{2s(t)} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{-(2k)^2 t}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} \varphi_{sk} e^{\frac{-(2k)^2 t}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} - \int_0^t j(\tau) d\tau} \\
 & + \frac{\pi}{2s(t)} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{-(2k)^2 t}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} \left(\frac{1}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi f_{sk} e^{\frac{-(2k)^2 t}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} - \int_0^\tau j(\tau) d\tau} d\tau \right) \tag{6} \\
 & - \frac{1}{s(t)} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} f_{sk}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2. Show the set $\{u(t)\} = \{u_0(t), u_{ck}(t), u_{sk}(t), k = 1, \dots\}$ of continuous functions on $[0, T]$ which satisfy the condition

$$\|u(t)\| = \frac{\max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |u_0(t)|}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |u_{ck}(t)| + \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |u_{sk}(t)| \right)$$

is the norm in B . (B is the Banach spaces).

Theorem 1. Let the assumptions (A1)-(A3) be satisfied then the solution of system (1)-(4) has exist solutions.

Proof. If we apply an iteration to equation (5), the following functions are obtained:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_0^{(N+1)}(t) &= u_0^{(0)}(t) + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi f(x, t, u^{(N)}) dx dt, \\
 u_{ck}^{(N+1)}(t) &= u_{ck}^{(0)}(t) \\
 &+ \frac{2}{\pi(1+\varepsilon(2k)^2)} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi e^{\frac{-(2k)^2(t-\tau)}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} - \int_0^\tau j(\tau) d\tau} \cos 2kx f(x, t, u^{(N)}) dx dt, \\
 u_{sk}^{(N+1)}(t) &= u_{sk}^{(0)}(t) \\
 &+ \frac{2}{\pi(1+\varepsilon(2k)^2)} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi e^{\frac{-(2k)^2(t-\tau)}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} - \int_0^\tau j(\tau) d\tau} \sin 2kx f(x, t, u^{(N)}) dx dt, \\
 u_0^{(0)}(t) &= \varphi_0 e^{-\int_0^t j(\tau) d\tau}, \quad u_{ck}^{(0)}(t) = \varphi_{ck} e^{\frac{-(2k)^2 t}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} - \int_0^t j(\tau) d\tau}, \\
 u_{sk}^{(0)}(t) &= \varphi_{sk} e^{\frac{-(2k)^2 t}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} - \int_0^t j(\tau) d\tau}.
 \end{aligned}$$

From the conditions of the theorem, we have $u^{(0)}(t) \in B, t \in [0, T]$.

Applying Cauchy inequality, Lipschitz condition, Hölder inequality, Bessel inequality, taking the maximum of both side, finally we have the following inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} \|u^{(1)}(t)\| &\leq \frac{\max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \|u_0^{(1)}(t)\|}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \|u_{ck}^{(1)}(t)\| + \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \|u_{sk}^{(1)}(t)\| \right) \\ &\leq \frac{\|\varphi_0\|}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (\|\varphi_{ck}\| + \|\varphi_{sk}\|) \\ &\quad + \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \|b(x,t)\| \|u^{(0)}(t)\| \\ &\quad + \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) M. \end{aligned}$$

From the conditions of the theorem $u^{(1)}(t) \in B, t \in [0, T]$.

Same estimations for the step N ,

$$\begin{aligned} \|u^{(N+1)}(t)\| &\leq \frac{\max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \|u_0^{(N)}(t)\|}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \|u_{ck}^{(N)}(t)\| + \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \|u_{sk}^{(N)}(t)\| \right) \\ &\leq \frac{\|\varphi_0\|}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (\|\varphi_{ck}\| + \|\varphi_{sk}\|) \\ &\quad + \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \|b(x,t)\| \|u^{(N)}(t)\| \\ &\quad + \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) M. \end{aligned}$$

Since $u^{(N)}(t) \in B, t \in [0, T]$ and from the conditions of the theorem, we have $u^{(N+1)}(t) \in B, t \in [0, T]$.

$$\{u(t)\} = \{u_0(t), u_{ck}(t), u_{sk}, k = 1 \dots\} \in B.$$

By the same estimations for (6):

$$\begin{aligned} \|j^{(1)}(t)\| &= \left\| \frac{s'(t)}{s(t)} \right\| + \frac{\pi^2}{4\sqrt{6}s(t)} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \|\varphi_{ck}''\| \\ &\quad + \frac{\pi}{\|s(t)\|} \left(1 + \frac{\sqrt{6}}{12} + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{12} \right) \|b(x,t)\| \|u^{(0)}(t)\| \\ &\quad + \frac{\pi}{\|s(t)\|} \left(1 + \frac{\sqrt{6}}{12} + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{12} \right) \|f(x,t,0)\|. \end{aligned}$$

In the same way, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|j^{(N+1)}(t)\| &\leq \left\| \frac{s'(t)}{s(t)} \right\| + \frac{\pi^2}{4\sqrt{6}s(t)} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \|\varphi_{ck}''\| \\ &\quad + \frac{\pi}{\|s\|} \left(1 + \frac{\sqrt{6}}{12} + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{12} \right) \|b(x,t)\| \|u^{(N)}(t)\| \\ &\quad + \frac{\pi}{\|s\|} \left(1 + \frac{\sqrt{6}}{12} + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{12} \right) M. \end{aligned}$$

Since $u^{(N)}(t) \in B, t \in [0, T], j^{(N)}(t) \in C^1[0, T]$ and from the conditions of the theorem, we have $j^{(N+1)}(t) \in C^1[0, T]$.

$$\begin{aligned} u^{(1)}(t) - u^{(0)}(t) &= \frac{(u_0^{(1)}(t) - u_0^{(0)}(t))}{2} \\ &\quad + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[(u_{ck}^{(1)}(t) - u_{ck}^{(0)}(t)) + (u_{sk}^{(1)}(t) - u_{sk}^{(0)}(t)) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Applying Cauchy inequality, Bessel inequality, Hölder inequality, Lipschitz condition in the last equation, taking maximum of both side of the last inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} \|u^{(1)}(t) - u^{(0)}(t)\| &= \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} - \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \|b(x,t)\| \|u^{(0)}(t)\| \\ &\quad + \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} - \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \|f(x,t,0)\|. \\ A &= \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} - \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \left[\|b(x,t)\| \|u^{(0)}(t)\| + \|f(x,t,0)\| \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Applying Cauchy inequality, Hölder inequality, Lipschitz condition and Bessel inequality to the last equation and taking maximum of both side of the inverse coefficient, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|j^{(1)}(t) - j^{(0)}(t)\| &\leq \frac{\pi}{\|s(t)\|} \left(1 + \frac{\sqrt{6}}{12} + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{12} \right) \|b(x,t)\| \|u^{(1)}(t) - u^{(0)}(t)\| \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{\pi TM}{\|s(t)4\sqrt{3}\|} + \frac{\pi^2 T}{\|s(t)4\sqrt{6}\|} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |\varphi_{ck}''| \right) \|j^{(1)}(t) - j^{(0)}(t)\|, \end{aligned}$$

$$B = \frac{\pi}{\|s(t)\|} \left(1 + \frac{\sqrt{6}}{12} + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{12} \right),$$

$$C = \left(\frac{\pi TM}{\|s(t)4\sqrt{3}\|} + \frac{\pi^2 T}{\|s(t)4\sqrt{6}\|} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |\varphi_{ck}''| \right).$$

$$\|j^{(1)}(t) - j^{(0)}(t)\| \leq \frac{B}{1-C} \|b(x,t)\| \|u^{(1)}(t) - u^{(0)}(t)\|,$$

$$\|u^{(2)}(t) - u^{(1)}(t)\| \leq \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \|b(x,t)\| \|u^{(1)}(t) - u^{(0)}(t)\|$$

$$+ \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \frac{BT}{1-C} M \|b(x,t)\| \|u^{(1)}(t) - u^{(0)}(t)\|.$$

$$\|u^{(2)}(t) - u^{(1)}(t)\| \leq \left\{ \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{BT}{1-C} \right) \right\} A \|b(x,t)\|.$$

For the step N :

$$\|j^{(N+1)}(t) - j^{(N)}(t)\| \leq \frac{B}{1-C} \|b(x,t)\| \|u^{(N+1)}(t) - u^{(N)}(t)\|,$$

$$\|u^{(N+1)}(t) - u^{(N)}(t)\| \leq \left\{ \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{BT}{1-C} \right) \right\}^N \frac{A}{\sqrt{N!}} \|b(x,t)\|^N.$$

by the We'erstrass M test we deduce from (9) that the series $\sum_{N=0}^{\infty} \|u^{(N+1)}(t) - u^{(N)}(t)\|$ is uniformly convergent to an element

of B . However, the general term of the sequence $\{u^{(N+1)}(t)\}$

may be written as $u^{(N+1)}(t) = u^{(0)}(t) + \sum_{n=0}^N \|u^{(n+1)}(t) - u^{(n)}(t)\|$, so

the sequence $\{u^{(N+1)}(t)\}$ is uniformly convergent to an element of B because the sum on the right is the N th partial

sum of the aforementioned uniformly convergent series. So $u^{(N+1)}(t) \rightarrow u^{(N)}(t)$, $N \rightarrow \infty$, then $j^{(N+1)}(t) \rightarrow j^{(N)}(t)$, $N \rightarrow \infty$.

Therefore $u^{(N+1)}(t)$ and $j^{(N+1)}(t)$ converge in B and $C[0, T]$, respectively.

Now let us show that there exists u and j such that

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} u^{(N+1)}(t) \rightarrow u^{(N)}(t), \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} j^{(N+1)}(t) \rightarrow j^{(N)}(t).$$

$$\|u(t) - u^{(N+1)}(t)\| \leq \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \|b(x, t)\| \|u(t) - u^{(N+1)}(t)\|$$

$$+ \left\{ \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{BT}{1-C} \right) \right\}^N \frac{A}{\sqrt{N!}} \|b(x, t)\|$$

$$+ \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) M \|j(t) - j^{(N)}(t)\|,$$

$$\|j(t) - j^{(N+1)}(t)\| \leq \frac{B}{1-C} \|b(x, t)\| \|u(t) - u^{(N+1)}(t)\|.$$

Apply Gronwall's inequality to last equations and taking maximum of both side of the last inequality, we have

$$\|u(t) - u^{(N+1)}(t)\|^2 \leq 2 \left[\frac{A}{\sqrt{N!}} \left(\left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{BT}{1-C} \right) \right)^{N+1} \|b(x, t)\| \right]^2$$

$$\times \exp 2 \left(1 + \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{BT}{1-C} \right) \right)^2 \|b(x, t)\|^2.$$

$$\|j(t) - j^{(N+1)}(t)\| \leq \frac{B}{1-C} \|b(x, t)\| \|u(t) - u^{(N+1)}(t)\|.$$

We obtain $u^{(N+1)}(t) \rightarrow u(t)$, $j^{(N+1)}(t) \rightarrow j(t)$, $N \rightarrow \infty$.

The proof is over.

Theorem 2. Let the assumptions (A1)-(A3) be satisfied then the solution of system (1)-(4) has unique solutions.

Proof. (1)-(4) has two solutions $u(x, t), k(x, t)$ and $j(t), l(t)$. Applying Cauchy inequality, Hölder inequality, Lipschitz condition and Bessel inequality to $|u(t) - k(t)|$ and $|j(t) - l(t)|$, we have

$$\|u(t) - k(t)\| \leq \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) M \|j(t) - j^{(N)}(t)\|$$

$$+ \left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \left(\int_0^t \int_0^\pi b^2(\xi, \tau) |u(\tau) - k(\tau)|^2 d\xi d\tau \right)^{\frac{1}{2}},$$

$$\|j(t) - l(t)\| \leq \frac{B}{1-C} \left(\int_0^t \int_0^\pi b^2(\xi, \tau) |u(\tau) - k(\tau)|^2 d\xi d\tau \right)^{\frac{1}{2}},$$

$$\|u(t) - k(t)\| \leq \left[\left(\sqrt{\frac{T}{\pi}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{3}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{B}{1-C} \right) \right]$$

$$\times \left(\int_0^t \int_0^\pi b^2(\xi, \tau) |u(\tau) - k(\tau)|^2 d\xi d\tau \right)^{\frac{1}{2}},$$

applying Gronwall inequality to the last equation, we have

$$u(x, t) = k(x, t), j(t) = l(t).$$

The proof is over.

3. Conclusions

The inverse problem regarding the simultaneously identification of the time-dependent source and the temperature distribution in one-dimensional quasilinear {pseudo}parabolic equation with periodic boundary and integral overdetermination conditions has been considered. In the article, the existence and uniqueness of the problem have been analyzed.

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